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TSC22D4 gene activation in Crohn's Disease.

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Tsc22d family members function nutrient sensing as part of an apparatus operating in energy homeostasis. We measured total transcription in the blood of humans with Crohn's Disease to define molecular mechanisms underlying disease at the cellular level using an unbiased approach through transcriptomic methods. We report here discovery of Tsc22d4 activation in the tissues of humans with Crohn's Disease. The high message count observed in RNA-sequencing from humans with Crohn's Disease for the Tsc22d4 gene indicates the presence of an underlying and basic molecular defect in nutrient sensing and energy homeostasis in the inflammatory bowel disease, Crohn's Disease.